

S P A T I A L

SPATIAL

Project Presentation Deck

SPATIAL project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101021808.

THE CHALLENGE.

Artificial Intelligence is dominated by the United States and China

- The 2 biggest economic poles
- **USA:** Audio & Natural Language Processing; Autonomous Robotics; Connected & Automated Vehicles
- **China:** New patents

How to position Europe as a frontrunner in AI.

A strategy centred around two pillars

EXCELLENCE

TRUST

Address specific features of AI technologies that make the application and enforcement of legislation challenging and generate high risks

RESEARCH GAPS.

DATA MODEL TRAINING

How data is influencing the behaviour of the AI systems

BIAS

PRIVACY

DATA POISONING

BLACK-BOX AI

Understanding how the systems are making safe decisions

EXPLAINABILITY

RISK LEVELS

TRANSPARENCY

OUR MISSION.

Achieve
Trustworthy AI
in cybersecurity
solutions.

Delivering building blocks to
enforce **data privacy**,
resilience engineering, and
legal-ethical accountability

OUR VISION.

The work on **social and technical aspects** will serve as a stepping stone to establish a **governance and regulatory framework for AI-driven security in Europe.**

OUR GOALS.

Transparency and Explainability

Verification and validation SW + HW mechanisms for security solution development

Explainability Metrics |
 Accountability Algorithms |
 Distillation for pre-trained Models |

Resilience and Privacy

Enhance resilience in the training and deployment of AI in decentralized, uncontrolled environments

Homomorphic Encryption |
 Privacy-preserving Computing |
 Risk Assessment |

OUR GOALS.

Societal Impact for Uptake

Provide adoption and adaptation specifications to reduce complexity of integration

Requirements and KPIs |
Guidelines |
Validation in use cases |

Education and Skills Building

An educational module to raise awareness and provide technical, ethical and legal skills

MOOC |
Knowledge fast-track |
Based on 'Elements of AI' |

USE CASE 1 - Privacy-preserving AI on the Edge

- **CHALLENGE:** Assess the performance of privacy-preserving ML deployed on edge computing nodes (telco environment)
- **IMPACT:** Protect user's sensitive data from devices. Enable 3rd party AI solutions to run securely and accountable in Network Virtualized infrastructure

USE CASE 2 - Cybersecurity

Analysis of 5G/4G/IoT Networks

- **CHALLENGE:** Improve current network security techniques in data infrastructure to become more resilient to attacks
- **IMPACT:** Validate the explainability and resiliency of SPATIAL security analysis in real-world 4G/5G/IoT framework

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USE CASE 3 – Emergency eCall System

- **CHALLENGE:** Accountable and transparent algorithms for smart data (eHealth) analysis and actuation in critical services
- **IMPACT:** Validation in a eCall communications demonstrator, automatically triggering Next Generation emergency calls

USE CASE 4 – Resilient Cybersecurity Analytics

- **CHALLENGE:** Evasion and poisoning attacks against and defences for ML models used in cybersecurity
- **IMPACT:** Implementing prototypes of dynamic attack detection systems and experiment with attack tactics to study their extent and key risks

W / T H[®]
secure

S P A T I A L

OUR TEAM.

StandICT.eu

ARCADIAN-IoT

ERATOSTHENES

INDUSTRIAL CYBERSECURITY

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Thank You

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